

On Needs about Depletion Chain Visualisation and Simplification

Lorenzo Canzian¹, Davide Manzione^{1,*}, Daniele Tomatis¹, Alain Hebert²

¹*newcleo SA, Via Giuseppe Galliano, 27, 10129 Torino TO, Italy;*

²*Polytechnique Montréal, Institut de Génie Nucléaire, Montréal, Quebec H3C 3A7, Canada*

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ABSTRACT

Accurate depletion calculations rely on solving the Bateman equations, which describe the evolution of nuclides through radioactive decays and neutron-induced transmutations. These processes are represented through depletion chains, which can include thousands of nuclides. This makes their construction, representation, and simplification a non-trivial task. Several computer codes have been developed to solve the Bateman equations. Some of these rely on simplification algorithms to reduce the complexity of the chains. The strategies adopted by different codes to simplify depletion chains vary widely, and no common standard currently exists. This lack of consistency complicates the comparison of results across tools. This work discusses the need for a dedicated tool for the simplification and validation of depletion chains. Such a tool shall provide clear graphical representations of decay and transmutation pathways, offer multiple simplification approaches, and ensure compatibility with commonly used nuclear analysis codes. A tool with these capabilities is under development at *newcleo*. The present study aims to identify the key features the tool should have to meet the users' needs.

Keywords: Nuclide chain, chain simplification, chain visualisation, burnup, dose.

1. INTRODUCTION

Depletion is the process by which nuclides concentration in a system varies due to transmutations and decays. For example, in nuclear reactors, some of the fissile nuclides can undergo fission. This is a process in which the parent nuclide splits into two or more daughter nuclei, known as fission products (FP). Alongside fission, radioactive decay and other neutron-induced reactions also contribute to the evolution of the nuclide inventory. This evolution can be represented through depletion chains, showing sequences of nuclides connected by decay and reaction pathways. The time-dependent behaviour of each nuclide's concentration in such a chain is described by the Bateman equation.

There are many scientific fields where the knowledge of depletion chains plays a central role in describing a particular phenomenon. In geology, some of the techniques used for sample dating are based on the knowledge of the uranium chains [1]. In medicine, radioisotopes are used for both diagnostics and therapy purposes. The choice of a radioisotope is guided by an understanding of its production and decay, which determine its clinical suitability, availability, and disposal requirements. Radiochemical studies require precise knowledge of the materials produced within a nuclear reactor, as this information is essential for analyzing safety issues such as radiation exposure and corrosion [2]. In nuclear engineering, depletion chains play a crucial role in many fields:

- In reactor physics, the solution of Bateman equation is required to represent reactivity effects in both normal operation conditions and accidental situations. Depletion of burnable poison and core burnup, i.e. the evolution of fuel isotopic composition during irradiation, must also be accurately predicted. These calculations are needed both at the lattice level and for full-core models [3].

*davide.manzione@newcleo.com

- Some fission products play an important role in fuel performance analyses such as rod pressure increase by gas release or pellet swelling [4].
- Reprocessing and waste management is strongly impacted by the decay of the radionuclides present in nuclear fuel. Solution of Bateman equation in out-of-core conditions, with a longer time-scale, is a specific need.

A complete depletion chain retrieved from nuclear data files, such as ENDF libraries, can include over 3000 nuclides. Handling such extensive information requires balancing precision and computational cost. While a full depletion chain can provide a deep understanding into the decay and transmutation pathways of the analysed system, it can also result in significant computational overhead. Chain simplification allows reducing memory occupation for the whole core material inventory and ill-conditioning of matrices used by the depletion solvers. Reduced memory footprint becomes crucial for full-core calculations with resolution taking on the physical fuel pin cells. Depending on the initial parameters and on the simplification method adopted, a depletion chain can have many different simplified versions. A comparison of the results obtained with different computer codes and simplification methods is therefore technically challenging. This highlights the need for a tool that seamlessly addresses the visualisation and the simplification of the depletion chains while providing interfaces towards the most common computer codes used in nuclear engineering. Providing a visual representation of a chain would be valuable for understanding the relationships occurring in a system while guiding the choice for the most appropriate simplification algorithm. In addition, such tool would facilitate the comparison of results obtained using different computer codes by writing and reading depletion chains that follow the exact structure expected by each code, ensuring compatibility.

Chain visualisation functionalities are already offered by other computer codes. Among the many tool available, we can cite JANIS [5], a software developed in Java and designed to facilitate the visualisation and manipulation of nuclear data. Its objective is to enable users of nuclear data to access numerical values and graphical representations without requiring prior knowledge of the storage format. However, it only provides the capability to plot decay reactions, leaving out the neutron-induced transmutations, and it does not provides any simplification method. A tool offering both visualisation and simplification capabilities is currently under development at *newcleo*. This paper aims to give an overview on the current state of the project with a focus on the users' needs and requirements.

This paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents common approaches for addressing depletion calculations. Section 3 gives an overview of some computer codes that implement solutions to the Bateman equation. Section 4 focuses on the many features a tool should have to meet the identified requirements related to the visualisation and the simplification of the depletion chains.

2. DEPLETION MODELLING AND SOLVING APPROACHES

A depletion chain describes the possible decay and transmutation pathways linking different nuclides. As decay and transmutation reactions occur, the number densities of the nuclides change over time. This process is modelled by the Bateman equations, a set of first-order differential equations describing the time evolution of the concentrations of the nuclides in the system. Equation (1) illustrate the Bateman equation for a given nuclide i [6]:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = \sum_{j \neq i} [(\gamma_{j \rightarrow i} \sigma_{f,j} \phi + b_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j + \sigma_{j \rightarrow i} \phi) N_j] - (\sigma_i \phi + \lambda_i) N_i + S_i. \quad (1)$$

where N_i is the atomic density of nuclide i , $\gamma_{j \rightarrow i}$ is the fractional fission product yield of nuclide i from fission of nuclide j , $\sigma_{f,j}$ is the microscopic fission cross section of nuclide j , ϕ is the neutron flux, $b_{j \rightarrow i}$ is the branching ratio for a particular decay of nuclide i from nuclide j , λ_j is the decay constant of the isotope j , $\sigma_{j \rightarrow i}$ is the microscopic transmutation cross section of reaction $j \rightarrow i$, N_j is the atomic density of nuclide j , λ_i is the decay constant of isotope i , σ_i is the microscopic total removal cross section of

nuclide i , S_i is a possible external source of nuclide i . All the microscopic reaction rates given by the product of cross sections and the neutron flux are energy-integrated.

Considering all the involved nuclides, the resulting system of equations can be expressed in matrix form as:

$$\frac{d\vec{N}}{dt} = \mathbf{A}\vec{N} + \vec{S}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the depletion matrix containing all decays and transmutations coefficients and \vec{S} represents the external source. If the matrix \mathbf{A} is considered time-independent, the solution of Equation (2) is given by:

$$\vec{N}(t) = e^{\mathbf{A}t}\vec{N}_0 + \int_0^t dt' e^{\mathbf{A}(t-t')}\vec{S}(t'), \quad (3)$$

where \vec{N}_0 is a vector containing the initial nuclide densities. The rank of the coefficient matrix \mathbf{A} depends on the number of involved nuclides, that is the size of \vec{N} . The presence of nuclides with decay constants differing by many orders of magnitude, as well as the contribution of certain reaction channels, makes the whole problem stiff.

In literature, different approaches for solving the Bateman equation are proposed [7]. One well-known approach uses approximate methods to solve equations involving the matrix exponential expanded as a series. One example of this is the *Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method* (CRAM), which relies on the best rational approximation for minimizing the largest absolute error on the matrix exponential solution [8]. This procedure is inherently stable in case of short-lived isotopes. However, current implementations are limited to an approximation of the matrix \mathbf{A} in time that is piecewise constant.

Another approach manages directly Equation (1). This class of methods is called *linear chain methods* [6]. The idea is to decompose the chain structure into a series of linear transformations that are then solved individually. These methods are popular for reprocessing and waste management studies.

Purely numerical strategies, such as the Runge-Kutta method, are popular in reactor physics applications [9]. The effectiveness of these methods depends on the stiffness of the Bateman equation, which requires specific treatment for the saturation of short lived isotopes. These numerical approaches are compatible with matrix \mathbf{A} approximations over time that are piecewise polynomial.

When using these methods to deal with large and complex chains, it is necessary to identify the optimal compromise between precision and computational speed. Hence, simplification algorithms are used to speed up the process [8][10][11][12][13]. The choice of a simplification algorithm is case-dependent, as it is based on the specific application.

3. OUTLINE OF CODES IMPLEMENTATION FOR DEPLETION PROBLEMS

When designing a new application for depletion problems, it is essential to conduct a preliminary analysis that evaluates different computer codes to investigate how compatibility between these softwares and a dedicated tool for depletion chain can be assured. This analysis should focus on the following key features:

- data format and structure used to store and read chains;
- the methods implemented for solving the Bateman equation;
- the simplification algorithms.

Depletion calculations are offered by several computer codes applied in nuclear engineering. Among these codes, the depletion functionalities implemented in OpenMC, DRAGON5 and ERANOS are discussed in the following with a focus on the aforementioned key features.

OpenMC is a MonteCarlo neutron and photon transport simulation code [14]. It builds the depletion

matrix from an XML file provided by the user, describing the decay chain according to a specific structure. However, OpenMC does not provide any XSD schema file as a reference for validation purposes. OpenMC employs CRAM to solve the Bateman equation for depletion. Generally, a trade-off should be considered between the accuracy of the solution method and its computational cost. In the case of transport-coupled depletion, these costs are driven almost entirely by the time to compute the transport solution, i.e., to evaluate \mathbf{A} for a given nuclide density vector \mathbf{N} . Consequently, the cost of a method scales with the number of \mathbf{A} evaluations that are performed. Regarding the simplification of depletion chains, OpenMC does not provide any built-in algorithm to automatically simplify a chain based on user-defined criteria.

DRAGON5 is a neutron transport lattice computer code based on a deterministic approach [15]. It includes several methods for solving the Boltzmann transport equation and Bateman depletion equation. DRAGON5 retrieves depletion chain data as part of the DRAGLIB libraries, which also contain microscopic cross sections and *kinetic energy released in matter* (KERMA) factors. Depletion data in the DRAGLIB is created using a specific post-processing module, named DRAGR, which is included in the NJOY2016 cross section processing code [16, 17]. The DRAGR module implements a simplification algorithm which is based on a user-specified list of nuclides that must be present in the final output. A lumping procedure follows, as depicted in Figure 1. This is based on concentrating the information of the lumped isotopes, such as decay energy and FP yields, and adding them to the corresponding mother and daughter isotopes, respectively.

Figure 1. Lumping of a depletion chain in DRAGR.

ERANOS (*European Reactor ANalysis Optimized calculation System*) provides data libraries, deterministic codes and calculation procedures developed for fast reactors cores. Data libraries are derived from the JEFF nuclear evaluated files using NJOY and CALENDF (*Computer-Aided Library for Evaluated Neutron Data Files*) codes [18]. NJOY processes evaluated nuclear data into multigroup cross sections, angular distributions and emitted spectra. CALENDF complements this by generating probability tables and self-shielding factors. Then, the burnup module calculates isotopic concentration evolution for actinides, fission and activation products. Chain files are provided by the users in a text format containing a list of heavy metals and fission products in the chain. ERANOS does not provide any built-in algorithms to automatically simplify depletion chains based on user-defined criteria.

4. NEWCLEO'S TOOL FEATURES

The analysis of the key features mentioned in Section 3 contributes to the definition of users' needs and how these can be translated into a set of requirements. A dedicated software (in the following referred to as the *tool*) is currently under development at *newcleo*. The version 1.0 of *tool* is planned to be released publicly on Github. It will include a complete workflow allowing users to provide, plot, simplify and export a depletion chain. This section presents the requirements and features that have already been implemented, as well as those that will be included in future releases.

The *tool* is written in Python to provide well-structured and intuitive interfaces to its core functionalities via its *Application Programming Interfaces* (APIs). This guarantees that users can develop automation scripts effortlessly and incorporate the tool into their own workflow. The *tool* is designed to support two core functionalities: visualisation and simplification. These functionalities can operate independently or sequentially. The visualisation step is intended to support users in providing a clear view of the relationships among the nuclides in a specific case study. From Section 3, ensuring compatibility between different computer codes is a key requirement which translates into the possibility for users to provide chain data coming from different tools. Specifically, the *tool* should be able to read chain files generated externally and write them in formats and structures that are compatible with the most commonly adopted nuclear computer codes. As these structures are defined by code developers, compatibility with each new code must be addressed separately according to the requested format. Alternatively, the option of automatically generating a chain file from an ENDF nuclear data library could also be considered, as this would enable users to access the *tool*'s functionalities independently of other nuclear computer codes. The *tool* adopts HDF5 (*Hierarchical Data Format*) as the reference data format for internal use due to its capacity to present chain data in a structured and accessible manner. Therefore, the input chain data files, for which compatibility is ensured, are converted to this format. When exporting chain files, users should be able to select a specific data format independently of the original input file. At present, *tool* only ensures compatibility with OpenMC as it can read and export chain files in the XML format adopted by OpenMC. Additionally, HDF5 chain files in the same format that the *tool* uses internally can be provided as input. Regardless of the format, a validation step is performed to ensure the correctness of the file structure and the contained information. In particular, a validation schema has been developed for OpenMC XML files to assess whether the input file fulfils the physical and functional requirements defined in OpenMC. Future releases will investigate the possibility of extending the input and output compatibility with the DRAGON and ERANOS codes. The former requires the capability to read and write HDF5 files in the APOLLO-LIB format, while the latter necessitates the interpretation of information contained in a simple text file.

A robust visualisation functionality is essential to ensure the clarity and accessibility of underlying data, even with the most complex chains. To accomplish this goal, the *tool* provides a classic $N - Z$ chain representation, in which nuclides, represented as circles (*nodes*), are positioned on a grid according to their *neutron number* N and *atomic number* Z . Other layouts should be considered: as an example, in addition to the classic representation, JANIS offers a compact $(N - Z) - Z$ layout and an $A - Z$ one (with A representing the *mass number* $A = N + Z$). Radioactive decays and neutron-induced reactions among nuclides are represented by arrows (*links*) connecting *nodes*. Achieving a clean visual representation requires the plotting algorithm to avoid intersections between *links* and *nodes*, while keeping those between *links* to a minimum. The same clarity is required when positioning *labels* as they carry out information about the represented transformations. In this sense, the *tool* ensures that *links* do not overlap *labels*, and that different *labels* do not intersect with each other. Figure 2a and Figure 2b show how the plotting algorithm, based on the LaTeX package Tikz [19], currently handles the metastable states and the overlapping of *links*, *nodes* and *labels*. Additionally, Figure 3 provides an example of a depletion chain. The starting nuclide is ^{90}Sr and the representation ends with the second generation of daughter nuclides. Fission products are represented by orange contour lines, while stable and starting nuclides are filled with brown and blue, respectively. Decays and transmutations *links* are coloured using two different colour palettes.

A dedicated *Graphical User Interface* (GUI) should be made available to enhance the user experience. This GUI would enable users to set plot parameters (e.g., the starting nuclides and the number of nuclide generations) and visualise the resulting chain in a graphical editor. Users should be able to customise the layout of the automatically generated plot as well as the visual rendering of the plot elements (e.g., by adopting a greyscale).

Chain simplification is an important feature that would allow users to remove nuclides that are not significant in their specific use case. Common approaches include:

Figure 2. The figure show how the current version of the plotting algorithm handles intersections between labels and the placement of edges around the nodes.

Figure 3. First two daughter generations of ^{90}Sr chain produced from OpenMC chain file.

- Adopting of a threshold for some key parameters (e.g., the half-life). Nuclides falling below this specified limit, would be simply lumped while still conserving decay energies, fission yields and production rates.
- Reducing the number of FP in the system by introducing pseudo-nuclides to preserve decay heat while still reducing the number of tracked nuclides.
- Reducing the number of nuclides in the system by acting on the threshold value of an importance-related quantity.

Since the simplification of a depletion chain is always case-dependent, users should be able to provide both chain file and case-dependent data according to the adopted simplification method. The reaction rates, required in the depletion matrix of the Bateman equation, are an example of this kind of information since dependent on the flux spectrum. One of the most commonly used simplification methods is based on the lumping algorithm shown in Figure 1. At present, the *tool* implements this simplification method, producing a chain containing only the user-specified nuclides. The algorithm lumps together all the nuclides that produce the user-selected ones by radioactive decay. Each time a nuclide is removed from the chain, the information about yields and energies is preserved, along with all the links between the involved nuclides. To cover a wide range of applications, users should be able to choose the algorithm that best addresses to their needs. Chain visualisation capability brought by the *tool* can support users in the choice and in the preparation of the needed data. Future releases of *tool* should extend this capability to other simplification methods, with a focus on automation.

Comprehensive documentation is a fundamental component of any scientific software project. The *tool* is accompanied by comprehensive documentation ensuring users have a thorough understanding of the implemented simplification method and how to guarantee compatibility with OpenMC. To ensure clarity and accessibility of information for users, it is essential to maintain versioned and updated documentation alongside the source code. The approach adopted with *tool* relies on Sphinx, a tool for automatically generating documentation into well-formatted HTML and PDF files. The documentation has been integrated directly into the project repository, and it is maintained so to ensure that it remains synchronised with any changes made to the code.

Finally, to ensure the robustness and reliability of the project, a dedicated test suite is essential. A comprehensive testing framework ensures the correctness of the individual components, as well as a consistent behaviour by detecting regressions during development.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A tool for depletion chain visualisation and simplification could act as a unifying element between different computer codes, facilitating more effective comparison of results. This requirement can be met by the ability to read and write depletion chains in a variety of data formats. Chain visualisation should focus on the clarity of the plots, ensuring the avoidance of intersections between *links* and *nodes*, as well as between *labels*. In addition, intersections between *links* should be kept to a minimum. The adoption of the chain simplification algorithm is case-dependent. Therefore, it is important to provide several algorithms to support as many applications as possible. Finally, comprehensive documentation and a test suite contribute to the adoption and diffusion of the tool within the user community. A tool that meets these requirements is currently under development at *newcleo* and a first public release will be available on GitHub. Following this release, user feedback will be collected and improvements will be incorporated into future versions.

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